
Financial stress and Indigenous Australians

Robert Breunig, Syed Hasan, and Boyd Hunter (2018)
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Key findings

- The main determinants of Indigenous financial stress are similar to those of non-Indigenous households but have different effect sizes; and
- Indigenous households require substantially less income to avoid financial stress as household size increases than non-Indigenous households; and
- Indigenous financial stress is exacerbated by demand-sharing (“humbugging”) and is reduced by engagement in traditional hunting and gathering activities; and
- It is important when thinking about Indigenous deprivation and poverty to use Indigenous-specific equivalence scales.

What we knew

- Indigenous experience of financial stress is extensive and severe.
- The lack of reliable measures of income and expenditure for Indigenous Australians means that there are limited options for identifying distinct Indigenous-specific needs.
- Equivalence scales used to control for differences in the size, composition, and characteristics of households are often based on non-Indigenous or non-Australian studies that are most likely inappropriate for Indigenous populations.

What we do

- We use wave 14 of the Household Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) survey to examine the financial stress of non-Indigenous households in Australia.
- We further use the 2014-15 National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Social Survey (NAT-SSIS) to examine Indigenous financial stress.
- We estimate models of the determinants of financial stress for:
 - non-Indigenous Australians
 - non-remote Indigenous Australians
 - all Indigenous Australians
- We produce equivalence scales that are based upon the income required to equate the probability of experiencing financial stress among households of different sizes and types.

What we know now

- The determinants of financial stress are similar for Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians.
- The derived equivalence scales are quite different for Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians.
- Indigenous households in non-remote areas require more financial resources to avoid cash flow problems than non-Indigenous households with similar characteristics.

- Indigenous households in remote areas require fewer financial resources to avoid cashflow problems than non-Indigenous households with similar characteristics.
- Remote Indigenous households experience less hardship than non-Indigenous households with the same characteristics.
- Indigenous Australians manage large households better. The additional income required to be at a similar level of stress as household size grows is lower than for non-Indigenous households.
- Having lent a key card to someone else (a proxy measure of "humberging") is highly associated with the experience of financial stress.

What this means for policy

- Given that non-remote Indigenous households experience more financial stress even at the same level of income as non-Indigenous households, improved financial literacy, perhaps through the education system, could improve outcomes for Indigenous households.
- Income and employment provide the best protection against financial stress; improved employment and increased incomes for Indigenous households should be a priority.

Caveats

- Non-response rates associated with the financial stress questions are about 20% in both data.
 - If non-response is related to financial literacy, our results could understate financial stress.
 - If this relationship differs across Indigenous and non-Indigenous groups, our comparison of equivalence scales for the two groups may be mis-leading.
- Reports of financial stress are fundamentally subjective. Two individuals could experience the same financial circumstances and one could consider it a part of normal life and the other could report it as financial stress.

Where to now?

- Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians have separate, group specific equivalence scales for financial stress, highlighting the need for Indigenous-specific consumption based equivalence scales.
- Indigenous identifiers need to be included on future household expenditure surveys. This would allow researchers to:
 - produce Indigenous-specific equivalence scales on a regular basis.
 - compare financial stress, consumption and incomes of Indigenous and non-Indigenous households.
- Any policy intervention to improve Indigenous outcomes should be accompanied by rigorous quantitative evaluation supported by high-quality data.

More information

- Get the full working paper at: <http://ftp.iza.org/dp11221.pdf> or the published version at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/14754932>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au